

Programmable Integrated Silicon Photonics Waveguide Meshes: Optimized designs and control algorithms

(Invited Paper)

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Abstract—Programmable Integrated Photonics is a recent area of research that aims to integrate a very-large scale of reconfigurable photonic resources to enable flexible and versatile photonic integrated circuits. In this paper we review the state of the art of general-purpose waveguide mesh arrangements with a special focus on those that allow the synthesis of optical feedback loops. Moreover, we propose for the first time three alternative waveguide mesh topologies that decouple the performance and the geometry of previously reported architectures while achieving a higher- component density integration. This innovation is of special relevance to mitigate one of the main scalability limitations, the integration area. The paper finalizes with an introduction to control algorithms for waveguide mesh arrangements based on derivative methods and non-derivative methods. These control methods provide a proof for the self-reconfiguration of large-scale waveguide mesh arrangements. In particular, we apply the computational optimization algorithms to program a hexagonal waveguide mesh to emulate a 1x8 beamforming network and an optical filter based on an unbalanced MZI design. All in all, the paper comprises recipes to achieve truly practical software-defined photonic integrated circuits.

Index Terms—programmable photonics, reconfigurable circuits, signal processing, integrated circuits, control algorithms.

I. INTRODUCTION

PROGRAMMABILITY, re-usability, reconfigurability, versatility and flexibility are key features in past and future revolutions. Almost all technology-based research areas are severely impacted when these features are incorporated to their processes and performances, [1, 2]. For example, in electronics, the paradigm shift from application specific integrated circuits (ASPICs) to general-purpose electronic processors and Field-Programmable Gate Arrays had become one of the strongest bases of the third and fourth industrial revolutions, [3]. As another example, traditional network management is being progressively substituted by Software-defined networking, enabling a more efficient dynamic network configuration, [4]. Moreover, other areas like software-defined radio incorporate general-purpose processors and a set of widely employed hardware electronics and high-speed electronics to enable

dynamic configuration of communication protocols, frequency ranges and optimization algorithms, [5]. Photonics is not an exception. Closely mimicking the past electronic trends, in the last 50 years, light-based systems have evolved from the first proposals of discrete integrated components to the growth of a complete ecosystem tailored to produce Application Specific Photonic Integrated Circuits (ASPICs), [6-7]. As in electronics integrated circuits, the up-front non-recurring engineering costs (NRE) including custom mask tooling, design hours and specific process developments reduce the cost effectiveness for low-volume applications. Only few application fields like transceivers and datacenters have shown enough volume fabrication to compensate the overhead costs, [8].

Replicating a prior roadmap followed by electronics, in the last decade, the reconfigurability degree of photonic integrated components has been progressively increasing. The introduction of integrated optical actuators makes PICs configurable and programmable, modifying the light propagation conditions locally, either in amplitude or phase with the proper electrical control signals, [2]. The very-large scale integration of actuators is the base under the concept of general-purpose photonic integrated circuits. Highly-inspired, by the electronics processors, a general-purpose photonic processor incorporates widely-employed resources that are enabled, routed and selected on demand by software definition, [9, 10]. As a possible candidate for the core of this processor, recent advances in programmable photonics have demonstrated PICs relying on a very-large scale interconnection of a set of beam-splitters and phase actuators (aka. Tunable Basic Units (TBUs)) that, inspired by electrical FPGAs, allow the synthesis and programming of photonic integrated circuits discretized into primitive blocks of TBUs, [11-14].

In parallel, alternative waveguide mesh arrangements of TBUs allowing feed-forward-only propagation and multi-interferometry of the optical signal [15] have demonstrated promising results for quantum computing [16,17], as hardware accelerators for deep-learning applications [17] and general linear signal processing [19, 20].

In this paper, we focus our work on general-purpose

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waveguide mesh cores that enable the programmability of not only multi-interferometry feed-forward propagation of light but also optical signal feedback-loops and cavities. In particular we review the state-of-the-art and report optimized architectures to mitigate the scalability issues dealing with footprint and performance. The control and practical operation of such circuits is a current open research question. In Section III, we propose and demonstrate the use of computational optimization methods to enable a practical control and self-configuration of very-large scale PICs based on general-purpose waveguide mesh arrangements. Both derivative-based and non-derivative-based optimization techniques are proposed. We finish the paper with the conclusions and envisioning the future roadmap of multipurpose programmable photonic integrated circuits.

II. WAVEGUIDE MESH CORES

Figure 1(a) illustrates a conventional ASPIC example that includes an optical filter based on an add-drop ring resonator accessible through port 1 (p_1). The *through port* output is split by two ports, p_2 and p_3 . The latter terminates a waveguide 1.5 times larger than the former and includes a tunable phase actuator. The *drop-port* output is labeled as p_5 and an additional input port is defined by p_4 . Any minimal circuit upgrade or modification forces to start again a time-consuming and cost custom design-fabrication-test circle. As illustrated, the optical circuit design in (a) is composed of a well-organized set of fourteen waveguide elements, two phase shifters and two beam-splitters or tunable couplers. Moreover, the combination of these basic building blocks is enough to implement the vast majority of the most simple and complex photonic linear processing architectures. This premise is one of the two fundamentals of integrated waveguide meshes. A second key feature, is given by the fact that a common 4-port Tunable Basic Unit can be designed in many different ways to perform as a discrete delay line, an optical switch, a tunable coupler or a phase shifter by suitable programming of its control signals.

Under these premises, the combination and interconnection of a large-enough number of TBUs describing a waveguide mesh arrangement can be employed as a common hardware photonic platform to program a wide variety of photonic linear processing architectures and design parameters. As illustrated in Fig. 1(b), the independent configuration of each TBU either as a delay line (optical switch in cross or bar state), as a tunable coupler and/or as a phase shifter results in the emulation or synthesis of the circuit in Fig.1.(a).

In the previous example, the TBU interconnection follows a square mesh topology. Notwithstanding, circuit discretization, space and power consumption constraints play a critical role in the design of photonic circuits in general and of optical meshes in particular. The limited area available for growing the optical mesh, and the need to reduce to a minimum the number of switching elements required for implementing a set of optical core topologies call for a careful analysis of possible geometries for the mesh interconnection implementing the optical core.

A. Tunable Basic Units

Before considering the waveguide mesh analysis, it is

Fig. 1. (a) Schematic of a conventional photonic integrated circuit showing its discretization into waveguide elements, couplers and phase shifters, (b) waveguide mesh arrangement configuring the previous circuit and inset of different configurations of the Tunable Basic Unit.

essential to fully understand the tasks and fundamentals of its primitive block, the TBU. A TBU is a 2x2 photonic component that employs beam-splitters and phase actuators to synthesize any coupling state and a common phase, independently. The interconnection between TBUs allows the user to synthesize a light-path on demand after fabrication by tuning each TBU defining the path where the optical signal goes through. Although there are multiple alternatives with different port count, tuning mechanisms and architectures [2, 14], the simplest approach is the TBU that relies on a balanced Mach-Zehnder Interferometer with an independent phase actuator on each arm. Most of the experimental responses to date had relied on this configuration and employ thermo-optic phase actuators as their tuning mechanism. Finding the optimum phase actuator technology is a current research area, where shorter lengths, reduced footprints, and low crosstalk and power consumption are the key performance indicators.

For a balanced MZI loaded with heaters on both arms, the splitting ratio is obtained by increasing the effective index due to the Joule effect in the upper or lower arm, producing a ϕ_{upper} and ϕ_{lower} phase shift respectively. Once set, a common drive in both heaters will provide a common phase shift, leading to independent control of the amplitude ratio and the phase, [11,16]. The simplified device matrix is defined by:

$$h_{TBU} = j e^{j\Delta} \begin{pmatrix} \sin \theta & \cos \theta \\ \cos \theta & -\sin \theta \end{pmatrix} \gamma e^{-j\omega BUD}, \quad (1)$$

where θ is $(\phi_{upper} - \phi_{lower})/2$, Δ is $(\phi_{upper} + \phi_{lower})/2$, and BUD is the time that takes the signal to go through the TBU or *basic unit delay*. The coupling factor K is then defined as $\cos^2(\theta)$.

The key features of a TBU are its *excess loss*, the *power consumption* to get a π -phase shift, total length including access waveguides or *basic unit length (BUL)*, the *BUD* and its longitudinal and transversal dimensions. They are precisely defined in [2].

B. General-purpose waveguide mesh design topologies

Very recently, alternative arrangements allowing both the synthesis of circuits including feedforward light propagation and optical feedback loops and cavities have been proposed and experimentally demonstrated.

1) Square waveguide meshes

Square waveguide mesh arrangements were the first proposed mesh topology. In their pioneering work, L. Zhuang and co-workers developed the concept where the interconnection of a large number of integrated balanced MZIs with two actuators could lead to the synthesis of a wide variety of PICs, [11]. As we saw in Fig. 1(b) this is achieved by discretizing conventional circuits into TBU with specific configurations. The proposed interconnection topology enables the routing of the optical signal path to follow orthogonal directions where the repetition of a given direction is not allowed for two consecutive TBUs. However, the topology is flexible enough to allow the synthesis of discrete waveguides or delay lines, tunable couplers as well as phase shifters and thus more complex building blocks like optical cavities and unbalanced MZIs.

2) Triangular waveguide meshes

The triangular waveguide mesh topology was proposed in [2, 21]. In this case, three TBUs describing longitudinal orientations of 0° (horizontal plane), 60° and -60° are interconnected through 6 points resulting in a triangular pattern, as illustrated in Fig. 2 (c1). Notice that the angle described by the longitudinal axis of two connected TBU is always 60° . Again, it can be shown that the interconnection scheme directly impacts on the degrees of freedom related to propagation directions for the light flow across two consecutive TBUs and consequently the allowed light-paths and circuits that can be implemented inside the arrangement. These are particularly useful to increase the integration density of TBUs, and to implement optical cavities with reduced cavity lengths. The triangular pattern achieves a better discretization resolution of unbalanced filter structures as compared to the square topology. They have been experimentally proven using Dual-Drive Directional Couplers as their TBU, [14]

3) Hexagonal waveguide meshes

As we saw for the square topology, the interconnection schemes between TBUs lead to regular uniform patterns with different topologies. The hexagonal topology was proposed in [2, 21]. It is a more efficient 3-point optical interconnection

scheme that resembles the arbitrary linear interferometer layouts with the difference that the proposed pattern also allows the synthesis of optical feedback loops and optical cavities. As illustrated in Fig. 2(a1), the light flow propagates through TBUs with longitudinal axis orientation of $\pm 60^\circ$ and 0° . However, in contrast to triangular waveguide meshes, the angle described by the longitudinal axes of two connected TBU is always 120° . The main advantages are their versatility and flexibility in fitting conventional circuit programming, their enhanced resolution compared to the two previous topologies and their synthesis efficiency. In addition, as opposed to the two previous patterns, it enables the synthesis of Sagnac mirrors, which are an essential building block for Fabry-Perrot Cavities. One of the main drawbacks of waveguide meshes, that is exacerbated in the hexagonal topology, is that the overall mesh footprint can be compromised if the longitudinal TBU dimension is too large. They have been experimentally proven showing the programming of multiple circuits [2, 12, 22-23].

4) Longitudinally parallel waveguide mesh arrangements

In the previous subsections, we saw that the proposed waveguide mesh circuit topologies arise from the selected optical interconnection nodes between TBUs following regular and uniform spatial geometries. We have given as much importance to the resulting pattern as to the interconnection scheme. However, in this section, we propose an optimized design layout for waveguide mesh arrangements, where we eliminate the dependencies between interconnection nodes and resulting topologies.

The motivation is three-fold. First, the current topologies are geometrically constrained by the patterns originated by their connections. In other words, once selected one of the interconnection topologies, our arrangement will inherit a series of capabilities, characteristics and performance metrics (analysed in [2, 21]). As a preliminary example, hexagonal topology is characterized by a better versatility, and programming flexibility but the associated footprint is compromised by the space-consuming hexagonal shapes.

Secondly, the integration of TBUs with different angular orientations implies the integration of some building blocks with performance metrics that are orientation-sensitive. In particular, 3-dB couplers like directional couplers or multi-mode interferometers designs are more reproducible and robust to fabrication if the longitudinal orientation is kept fixed. In addition, some phase actuators are orientation-sensitive and are more efficient if single or orthogonal orientations are maintained, [24, 25].

Finally, the fabrication costs are directly related to the total footprint of the integrated device. The use of the

aforementioned topologies results in an increment of the unused areas in the device, particularly in designs with longitudinally-large TBUs. Although it might be convenient to maintain a

safety gap for optical and tuning-derived crosstalk, we would like to decouple this parameter from the selected waveguide mesh interconnection scheme.

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram example of the implementation and interconnection of the (a1) hexagonal pattern and (a2) the longitudinally- parallel mesh topology homologue to the hexagonal optical interconnection, (b1) square pattern and (b2) the longitudinally- parallel mesh topology homologue to the square optical interconnection, (c1) triangular pattern and (c2) the longitudinally- parallel mesh topology homologue to the triangular optical interconnection, (d-e) examples of longitudinally-parallel implementations where a translation to a conventional uniform topology is not possible.

In the light of the previous considerations, we describe here the use of parallel waveguide meshes to potentially solve all the aforementioned issues. Since the main performance metrics are related to the optical interconnection schemes or optical nodes, there are multiple possibilities for the definition of their architectures. However, in contrast to the previous patterns, they benefit from maintaining all TBU with the same longitudinal orientation. Compared to the square, hexagonal and triangular lattices, more complex access paths are required in the definition of the TBU for their interconnection, however, their impact is mitigated in integration platforms with high index contrast due to the reduced bend radius.

Figure 2 illustrates the concept by comparing the previous topologies with their homologue parallel/flat configurations.

Note that the access waveguides sizes have been exaggerated to enhance the figure readability. Consider that if the bend radius in the access waveguide is small, the overall design footprint becomes narrower in the vertical direction much more than wider in the horizontal direction and the resulting integration density increases for every interconnection scheme. In addition, it can be shown that during the design of longitudinally-parallel meshes, there is more freedom to define the optical interconnection node between TBUs. In the non-parallel implementations, one is constrained to a set of few geometrical patterns. As an example, Fig. 3 (d-e) illustrates two alternative parallel waveguide mesh geometries that do not have a straightforward associated uniform topology.

An engineering/design process of alternative interconnection schemes results in different performance metrics like tuning *spatial resolution for cavities, delays* and *MZIs, replication ratio* that measure the programmability and versatility of the waveguide mesh for the task of programming conventional photonic integrated circuits, and *switching elements per area*, as defined in [2, 21]. Note that most of these figures of merit are relative to the optical interconnection scheme, so equivalent results are obtained for standard- and their associated longitudinally-parallel versions. This effect can be explained through graph-based theory, [26]. If we assign a vertex to each interconnection node, and an edge to the four signal flow possibilities in a 2x2 TBU, we will find that the number of edges and vertex and their interconnection schemes are equivalent for the standard and longitudinally-parallel designs. This property is known as *isomorphism* between the two graphs.

Finally, for most applications, the access waveguides that interconnect the TBUs should be of equal length in order to preserve the same *BUL* and *BUD* over the waveguide mesh. Also, a good design would reduce the number of bends and would try to compensate the number of bends and their orientation for every access waveguide. The design of this access path is straightforward in all the proposed arrangements. However, some applications might find useful a variable non-uniform BUL, giving birth to non-uniform waveguide meshes.

III. OPTIMIZATION METHODS FOR WAVEGUIDE MESH CORES

As the number of reconfigurable integrated components in a PIC increases the need for a control system and routines

enabling a practical use of the PIC becomes mandatory. Historically, the complexity of reconfigurable photonic circuits has been moderate and either manual or semi-automated iterative routines have been enough to enable their operation. The control system can be composed of electrical driving circuitry for the actuators an electrical circuitry to monitor the optical signals at specific points in the PIC and a logic unit to run the computational algorithms. Based on the feedback collected by the readout system, a microcontroller computes the new required driving signals for the actuators based on software routines. Examples of these schemes have been employed in the configuration of optical bank filters based on cascaded MZIs [27], optical ring resonators [28], and moderate-size multiport interferometers propagating in feed-forward waveguide mesh arrangements [18-20, 29]. In the latter circuits, the optical signal monitoring is located after each TBU, increasing the control system overhead and limiting the scalability of the circuit. In order to reduce the number of readout points, it has been theoretically proposed the use of external monitoring at the output ports in feedforward-only waveguide mesh arrangements, [30].

In this section we propose and demonstrate the use of optimization methods for the control and configuration of general-purpose waveguide mesh arrangements like the ones covered in the previous section. The main difference with the algorithms and architectures published to date is that we aim for an effective optimization method that allows us to configure waveguide mesh arrangements that allow both feedforward and optical feedback loops. Moreover, we aim for optimization algorithms that avoid signal preparation at the inputs and optimize the number of optical readouts. A straightforward approach consists of the integration of optical power monitors on every TBU output. Once obtained the coupling response of each TBU one can program the overall mesh by using global configuration algorithms, [31].

However, as in the case of feedforward-only arrangements, the integration of readouts at every TBU implies a serious limiting overhead for the PIC scalability both in its packaging and electrical interfacing and in the optical power budget. In order to relax this limit, we propose the reduction of the number of optical readouts points to every output port of the optical mesh, i.e. without internal monitoring.

The optical monitoring can be based on integrated photodetectors after collecting a portion of the signal through a directional coupler or by using advanced structures like CLIPP detectors [20] or low-efficiency optical monitors [32].

Then, we can develop and apply software routines that include adaptations of mathematical optimization methods to program the actuators and get the desired functionality of the system. Mathematical optimization methods deal with the problem of finding minima/maxima of a cost function. In our case, we define application-specific cost-functions. They are computed based on the specifications of the targeted functionality. As the proper algorithm, *per se*, the design of the cost function is essential for the success and faster convergence of the algorithm. The cost function can combine several features f and being multiplied by a correction factor (c) to

specify its weight in the final metric:

$$CF(\mathbf{v}) = \sum_n c_n f_n(\mathbf{v}), \quad (2)$$

where n is the number of features considered and \mathbf{v} is the vector including the variables that are tuned in the optimization process. In our present work, \mathbf{v} includes a set size equal to the double of the number of TBU enabled during the optimization ($2N_{TBU}$). The first half of elements deals with the differential drive and actuates only the upper phase shifter of each TBU. The second half deals with the common drive and actuates over the sum of both phase shifters in the TBU.

As far as features are concerned, an experimental demonstration would consider postprocessed data from the optical readout system. In the present work, we employ the data obtained by a scattering matrix analytical model derived in [13] that computes the scattering matrix $H(\mathbf{v})$ of the targeted waveguide mesh arrangement that considers the specified driving of each phase actuator (\mathbf{v}). In addition, we emulate the random passive initial state of real TBU imposing an additional phase term to the upper phase shifter. This value is not employed during the optimization process and is only considered for verification and monitoring. Although analytical solutions enable a safer and faster development environment, obtaining the scattering matrix is more computationally expensive and time consuming than obtaining the data for real readouts. For simplicity we will obviate that H is a function of \mathbf{v} in the formulation.

As an example, if our functionality is a programmed light-path between ports 3, 8 of a waveguide mesh arrangement we could define two features for the cost function before starting the minimization process of (2) as:

$$\begin{aligned} c_1 &= -1, & f_1 &= |H_{8,3}|^2, \\ c_2 &= 0.5, & f_2 &= \sum_{p=1}^P |H_{p,3}|^2, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $H_{o,i}$ is the optical field response from a channel defined by an input port i and an output port o .

Note that the first feature is accompanied by a negative correction factor to ensure that the minimization of the CF leads to the targeted functionality. The second feature aims to minimize the power in the remaining output ports during the optimization process.

The number of alternative computational optimization techniques is wide-ranging and they are applied in very different application fields. However, no computational optimization techniques have been proposed for general-purpose waveguide mesh arrangements. Here we will report optimization solutions to program the mesh arrangement of Fig. 3. These include the description of the targeted functionality, the definition of the engineered cost function and the development and application of the software-routine. The selected PIC is a general-purpose waveguide mesh arrangement composed of 36 TBUs based on a MZI, (72 phase actuators) and 24 optical outputs. Although the standard shape is employed, note that its application to the flattened longitudinally-parallel version would be equal.

Fig. 3. (a) Schematic of the waveguide mesh arrangement employed in the examples, (b) Targeted black-box system of a 1x8 beamsplitter with labelled ports equivalent to (a).

A. Derivative methods (First-order optimization algorithms)

For the minimization of the cost function, these set of techniques employ the multivariable generalization of the derivative of the CF for each variable in \mathbf{v} .

$$\mathbf{g} = \nabla_{\mathbf{v}} CF(\mathbf{v}). \quad (4)$$

The resulting vector \mathbf{g} is the gradient of the function and it provides the direction tangential to the error surface at the evaluation point defined by \mathbf{v} . This direction is employed to advance on the opposite way to progress in the minimization of the error function. A wide range of first-derivative optimization methods are reported in the literature, [34]. The simplest and more extended is the gradient-descent algorithm. It renders the next configuration state of our system by sequentially applying:

$$\mathbf{v}^t = \mathbf{v}^{t-1} - \eta \mathbf{g}, \quad (5)$$

where η is the learning rate. This hyper-parameter must be selected by the practitioner and regulates the step size between iterations. A large value can make the process converge earlier but can also lead to noisy results and prevent the algorithm to achieve the optimal value of \mathbf{v} .

A straightforward approach for computing the derivatives of the error function is to use finite differences approximation. This can be done by perturbing each variable in turn, and approximating the derivatives by the following expressions:

$$g_i = \frac{CF(v_i + \varepsilon) - CF(v_i)}{\varepsilon} + O(\varepsilon), \quad (6)$$

$$g_i = \frac{CF(v_i + \varepsilon) - CF(v_i - \varepsilon)}{2\varepsilon} + O(\varepsilon^2), \quad (7)$$

In (5) the gradient employs the evaluation of the CF in \mathbf{v} perturbing the position i by a small amount ε . In our case, we define ε equal to $0.3 \cdot 10^{-3}$ rads. The rationale behind is that the finite-differences approximation is better approximated if we are close to the evaluation point. However, the lower limit will be imposed by the resolution of our electrical drivers and the noise of the readout system. In (6) we see the central differences equation to get a significantly better approximation of the

gradient. However, the number of computational steps is almost doubled when compared to (5).

As the reader can infer, getting the gradient straightforwardly in a real waveguide mesh system, as proposed, implied performing the perturbation of one actuating variable, getting the associated CF from the postprocessed signal from the readout system, repeating the procedure with a negative perturbation and then computing (6). Then, this procedure is iterated for every optimization variable till getting the full vector \mathbf{g} . Next, we apply (5) to get the next actuation driving variables \mathbf{v}^t and if the exiting conditions are not achieved, we iterate again.

To enhance the convergence speed, and to overcome noisy gradients, we can make use of the momentum algorithm. It accumulates an exponentially decaying moving average of past gradient vectors \mathbf{v}_{mo} and use a proportion (α_{mo}) of it to set the new direction. The new \mathbf{v}^t is

$$\mathbf{v}^t = \mathbf{v}^{t-1} + (\alpha_{mo} \mathbf{v}_{mo} - \eta \mathbf{g}), \quad (8)$$

where α_{mo} is another hyper-parameter in the range [0,1) that determines the relation between the new gradient and the accumulated.

The following procedure incorporates the algorithm. If α_{mo} equal to 0 is selected, we get the conventional gradient descent.

procedure gradientDescent_momentum_mesh()

require: initial \mathbf{v} (can be random or 0)

require: set initial \mathbf{v}_{mo} to zeros.

setting η, α_{mo}

while (stopping conditions or maxiter)

 get gradient (Eq. (4 and 2))

 get next variable vector (Eq. (8))

end while

To test the procedure, we start with a first application. In this case we want to get the optimum actuation variables \mathbf{v}_{opt} to achieve a mesh performance equivalent to a 1x8 beam splitter as illustrated in Fig. 4 (b). Since the splitting by 8 will introduce a 9.03 dB penalty and, assuming average penalties of 0.1 dB per TBU. We will set our targeted channel loss to 10 dB. The selected input port will be port 6, whereas ports 13, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 22, will be the output ports.

These specifications can be translated to the following cost function variables to be evaluated in (2):

$$\begin{aligned} c_1 &= 1/8, c_2 = 0, c_3 = 1/8, \\ f_1 &= \sum_{op} \left(10 \log_{10} \left(|H_{op,6}|^2 \right) + 10 \right)^2, \\ f_2 &= \sum_{p \neq op} \left(10 \log_{10} \left(|H_{p,6}|^2 \right) \right), \\ f_3 &= \left(\begin{array}{l} \sum_{op} \max \left(10 \log_{10} \left(|H_{op,6}|^2 \right) \right) \\ - \min \left(10 \log_{10} \left(|H_{op,6}|^2 \right) \right) \end{array} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where op references the optical ports under use by this configuration. Note that, in this case, we have disabled the

information coming from the signals from the remaining ports in the second feature. As for the third feature, it considers the ripple of the channel to achieve a better cost function. This is an example of a cost function that employs spectral information, meaning that if low-speed diodes are employed a laser swept would be required in a real-system. Alternatively, a filtered WDM spectrum could be photodetected at each spectral channel, increasing the complexity of the system. The use of extra features and the consideration of non-used or secondary ports is particularly interesting for larger-scale waveguide meshes.

Figure 4 illustrates an example of the resulting optimization procedure where η, α_{mo} are $7.2 \cdot 10^{-2}$ and 0.8, respectively. First, in Fig. 4 (a), we can see the three $c_i f_i$ products and the CF for each iteration. By regulating the coefficients c_i we can weight their contribution in the overall CF. In this example, we appreciate that *feature 1* is the dominant until arriving to iteration 12. Then *feature 3*, which is proportional to the mean ripple becomes dominant until the end of the process. At iteration 45, the selected exiting criterium is satisfied, giving as a result the optimum \mathbf{v} . Here we selected the ripples mean value below 0.2 dB and a mean error in the channels of $c_i f_i = 0.12$. The latter was achieved at iteration 32. Figure 4(b) illustrates the coupling factor modification of each TBU during the optimization process. It is worth mentioning again that this data has not been employed during the optimization process and it is only employed for verification purposes. In Fig. 4 (c) we can see the power responses of every channel in the waveguide mesh arrangement. We can appreciate that the 8 targeted ports converge at the desired -10 dB-level. Since we did not included *feature 2* in (9), the optical crosstalk is slightly better than 10 dB for the unused channels at iteration 45. Both including the feature and adding more restrictive stopping conditions lead to an enhancement in the optical crosstalk with the unused ports.

In order to show the implications of the hyper-parameter selection we maintain the learning rate and ε fixed with the aforementioned values. Then we sweep the momentum coefficient α_{mo} from 0 (standard gradient descent) to 0.9 in steps of 0.1. For each value we perform 10 tests allowing a maximum of 300 iterations per test. Each test starts with random and unknown passive phases at each TBU. If the targeted exit conditions are achieved, then it exits the test and saves the best iteration. In this example the exit conditions are maintained as in the previous example.

We will consider that the ones that require more than 300 iterations do not properly converge. Figure 5 (a) illustrates the resulting values. We can appreciate that the optimum values of enhanced convergence are achieved by $\alpha_{mo} = 0.8$. In this case, they require less than 63 iterations to converge. Fig. 5 (b) represents the results where the momentum is fixed to 0.8 and the learning rate is varied, showing the impact of this hyper-parameter.

Fig. 4. (a) Cost function minimization versus iterations, (b) Coupling coefficient tuning during optimization process, (c) Optical power monitoring at every waveguide mesh output during the optimization process, (d) final normalized frequency response normalized to one single TBU delay. Only five spectral points are considered per channel.

In order to test the proper behavior of the algorithm, we perform the test with the optimal hyper-parameters 100 times and perform a statistical analysis of the achieved ripples, output mean error in the selected channels and the number of required iterations and operations performed. The analysis plotted in Fig. 6. is performed two times: in Fig. 6 (a) the feature 2 is not considered ($c_2 = 0$), and in Fig. 7 (b) the feature 2 is slightly considered ($c_2 = 0.01$). In short, the test reveals that a small impact in the definition of the cost function impacts over the

Fig. 5. (a) Test results containing the best iteration (convergence) for the 1x8 beamsplitter for (a) different momentums at a fixed learning rate of $7.2e-2$, (b) for different learning rates and fixed momentum of 0.8.

performance of the optimization process. In this case, the mean ripples values are slightly better when feature 2 is included, with no serious implications in overall process performance.

As a second application example, we want to synthesize an optical filter based on a MZI interferometer. In this case, we are going to specifically select the TBUs that we want to enable during the circuit optimization to achieve a lower-dimensional optimization variable space. This is particularly interesting in large-scale arrangements. Looking at the mesh depicted in Fig. 4 we can employ TBUs A7 and B10 as the input and output couplers of the interferometric structure, a long arm including TBUs C7, A6, B6, C10 and a shorter arm including TBUs B7, A10. As in the 1x8 beam splitter, we start by defining a new cost function. For this application, typical features of optical filters are Extinction Ratio (ER), insertion loss (IL) and bandwidth. After testing with more than 100 cost functions alternatives developed by choosing different features and weights, we appreciate the importance on the final selection on elevating the success or convergence rates. Indeed, we saw that in most iterations, minimizing some of the features led to an

Fig. 6. Statistical results obtained after performing the optimization process of the 1x8 beamsplitter 100 times. (a) feature 2 is not considered ($c_2 = 0$), and (b) the feature 2 is slightly considered ($c_2 = 0.01$).

increase of the others, being the origin of noisy gradients if weights (c_i) are not properly selected. Here one can obtain more optimum cost functions and/or use alternative computational optimization algorithms like conjugate gradient descent, RMSProp, Adam, to cite a few, [33]. As an alternative, we can develop specific routines for each application. For example, in this case, we developed a routine that employ two cost functions. The employed cost function for each iteration is selected depending on the current performance conditions, leading to better results when compared to straightforward use of a common CF. This approach, however, requires some knowledge about the fundamentals of the targeted circuit behaviour. Precisely, in this application example we employ a cost function that optimize the channel loss of the MZI filter when the channel loss is greater than 1.5 dB and selects the second cost function enabling a single TBU for the optimization of the ER.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left. \begin{aligned} c_1 &= 0.005, c_2 = 0, & \text{if } f_2 < -1.5 \text{ dB} \\ c_1 &= 0, c_2 = 0.5, & \text{if } f_2 > -1.5 \text{ dB} \end{aligned} \right\} \\
 f_1 &= \left(\begin{aligned} & \sum_{op} \max \left(10 \log_{10} \left(\left| H_{op,4} \right|^2 \right) \right) \\ & - \min \left(10 \log_{10} \left(\left| H_{op,4} \right|^2 \right) \right) \end{aligned} \right), \quad (10) \\
 f_2 &= \sum_{op} \left(10 \log_{10} \left(\left| H_{1,4} \right|^2 \right) \right),
 \end{aligned}$$

As an example of the obtained results, Fig. 7(a) illustrates the targeted MZI structure and the employed TBUs. Fig. 7 (b) illustrates the achieved filter performance, where the ER and IL parameters are depicted. Finally, Fig. 7 (c) illustrates the changes in the coupling response of each TBU involved in the optimization process.

As for the required reconfiguration times of the mesh, they are application sensitive. For the two approaches followed in this section, the starting driving configuration will set the initial \mathbf{v} . Then, the targeted application in the CF shape will require a certain amount of iterations to converge (N_{iter}). Each iteration internally computes the gradient with a number of operations approximately equal to the number of enabled actuators (N_{act}). Note that they are the double of the number of TBUs participating in the optimization process. For each actuation, the required time delay (τ) to tune the actuator, getting the necessary data from the readouts to build-up the cost functions and save the data is technology dependent. Thus, the total reconfiguration time is:

$$RT = N_{iter} N_{act} \tau, \quad (11)$$

Assuming an approximated τ of 1 ms, the reconfiguration times in the previous 1x8 beam splitter example results in a time delay in the range of 5.76ms and 21ms. These figures are doubled if central differences are employed, as in (6). The analytical model employed requires an approximated τ of 175 ms for 5 wavelength points. That translates into computational times of few minutes.

Fig. 7. (a) targeted unbalanced MZI architecture with labelled ports mapping the code of Fig. 4(a). (b) Resulting transfer function after optimization process with labelled performance and (c) coupling factor variation of the enabled TBUs during the optimization process. ER: Extinction Ratio, IL: Insertion loss.

B. Non-derivative methods (Zero-order optimization algorithms)

As the reader can infer, getting the gradient straightforwardly in a real waveguide mesh system, as proposed, means performing the perturbation of one actuating variable, getting the associated CF from the post-processed signal from the readout system, repeating the procedure with a negative perturbation and then computing (6). Then, this procedure is iterated for every optimization variable till getting the full gradient.

An alternative to the gradient computation is to employ non-derivative computational optimization methods, like the Nelder-Mead simplex algorithm, (N-M) [34]. It consists on a direct search computational optimization method that evaluates the cost function in the variable space and select the next evaluation point by comparison among a set of previously selected points. In this section we applied the N-M algorithm to the previous 1x8 example. Here, the stopping criteria relates to the decrement in the CF for a certain number of iterations. First, we applied a softer criterion where the process exits if the cost function is not reduced by 0.05 during 500 iterations. Then, we test another 100 trials of the method where the procedure terminates if the cost function is not reduced by 0.01 during 500 iterations. In addition, the vector \mathbf{v} is the active driving phase of each phase actuator.

An example of the optimization process is illustrated in Fig 8 for one of the cases employing the softer stopping criteria. We can see that the targeted performance has been achieved properly.

Figure 9 illustrates the statistical analysis. We can see that in this case, the use of a softer criterium results in better ripple reduction in the optical channel and better optical output approximation to -10 dB. Remember that the optical output error is given by feature 1 in (9). The cost to pay comes with an increment in the number of iterations. As opposed to derivative methods, here the number of operations is close to the number of iterations.

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Fig. 8. Results of the N-M algorithm in the 1x8 beamsplitter example: (a) Cost function minimization versus iterations, (b) final normalized frequency response normalized to one single TBU delay. Only five spectral points are considered per channel.

Fig. 9. Statistical results obtained after performing the optimization process of the 1x8 beam splitter 100 times employing a non-derivative method. (a) softer stopping criteria, (b) harder stopping criterion.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper we have reviewed the state-of-the-art of general-purpose waveguide mesh arrangements. These architectures are called to play a key role in future programmable photonic integrated circuits. However, the best performance is offered by an architecture that is more space-consuming when compared to the other alternatives. To compensate this, drawback, we have proposed a novel architecture that while implementing the same optical interconnection scheme allows the integration of every tuning element following the same longitudinal axis orientation. This innovation has been presented for all the existent mesh topologies and is expected to reduce the scalability issues and enhance the circuit robustness and performance.

Next, the large-scale integration of general-purpose waveguide meshes is currently limited by our capability to properly drive all the units automatically to get a desired functionality. In this work we have proposed the use of computational optimization methods as the basis to configure automatically the circuits. The actuation variables are optimized to reduce a cost function that is application-dependent. We provided a proof-of-concept that both gradient-based algorithms and non-derivative methods can succeed on this task. In the light of these results, a new generation of self-optimized photonic integrated circuits based on general-purpose waveguide mesh arrangements is envisioned. Future actions should be focused on applying alternative algorithms that allows a reduction on the number of iterations for noisy cost functions and on the development of more efficient cost functions.

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